

Run Overview Report

Project: Benjamin
Assay: Eukaryote Total RNA StdSens
Run: Run 102523C_10-25-2023_2-19-31 PM
Run Version: N/A

Acq. Analyst: DefaultUser
Acq. Time: 10/25/2023 2:19:32 PM
Signature: N/A

Virtual Gel Report

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Egram, Gel Lane and Result Table Report

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Well# Ladder

Well# Ladder

RNA Area: 54.08
 RNA Concentration: 160.00 ng/μl

Well# Ladder

Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.55	1.48	
	2	30.30	6.04	
	3	34.65	5.01	
	4	39.65	4.01	
	5	42.40	4.33	
	6	44.90	3.79	
	7	48.50	4.57	
	8	51.60	4.17	
	9	56.65	4.99	

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Well# 1 Sample 1

1

Well# 1 Sample 1

Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area
1	18S	43.35	44.85	2.05	2.23
2	28S	47.70	50.10	3.84	4.19

RNA Area: 91.59
 RNA Concentration: 271.01 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 1.88
 RQI: 4.5 ■

Well# 1 Sample 1

Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.55	1.69	
	2	37.32	1.05	
	3	41.11	0.49	
	4	42.21	0.85	
	5	43.16	0.50	

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Well# 1 Sample 1				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	6	43.91	1.89	
	7	46.70	1.99	
	8	48.60	2.66	

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Well# 2 Sample 2

Well# 2 Sample 2						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	42.80	44.95	1.72	2.43	
2	28S	47.85	50.10	1.42	2.00	

RNA Area: 70.84
 RNA Concentration: 209.60 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 0.82
 RQI: 3.9 ■

Well# 2 Sample 2				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.55	1.95	
	2	42.23	0.68	
	3	43.97	1.25	
	4	46.75	0.62	

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Well# 3 Sample 3

Well# 3 Sample 3						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	41.70	42.85	0.60	1.79	
2	28S	46.25	47.55	0.35	1.04	

RNA Area: 33.43
 RNA Concentration: 98.91 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 0.58
 RQI: 3.4 ■

Well# 3 Sample 3					
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments	
	1	23.55	1.89		
	2	42.28	0.52		

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Well# 4 Sample 4

Well# 4 Sample 4						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	41.90	43.05	0.21	1.81	
2	28S	45.90	47.55	0.19	1.62	

RNA Area: 11.46
 RNA Concentration: 33.91 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 0.90
 RQI: 3.6 ■

Well# 4 Sample 4				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.55	1.95	

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Well# 5 Sample 5

5

Well# 5 Sample 5						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	42.95	44.75	0.34	1.83	
2	28S	51.00	52.65	0.15	0.83	

RNA Area: 18.67
 RNA Concentration: 55.24 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 0.45
 RQI: 3.3 ■

Well# 5 Sample 5				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.55	1.77	

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Well# 6 Sample 6

6

Well# 6 Sample 6						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	41.65	42.90	3.56	1.47	
2	28S	44.85	48.10	10.50	4.34	

RNA Area: 241.61
 RNA Concentration: 714.90 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.95
 RQI: 8.1 ■

Well# 6 Sample 6					
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments	
	1	23.55	1.87		
	2	33.87	0.96		
	3	35.25	0.91		
	4	35.74	0.79		
	5	36.63	1.10		

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Well# 6 Sample 6				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	6	37.32	4.30	
	7	37.92	4.58	
	8	38.81	5.28	
	9	40.14	5.91	
	10	41.18	9.26	
	11	42.26	13.00	
	12	43.20	4.79	
	13	43.94	13.47	
	14	45.42	5.90	
	15	46.16	5.39	
	16	46.71	7.21	
	17	48.68	2.34	

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Well# 7 Sample 7

7

Well# 7 Sample 7

Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area
1	18S	43.20	44.80	17.92	5.26
2	28S	49.90	52.55	24.25	7.12

RNA Area: 340.73
 RNA Concentration: 1,008.18 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 1.35
 RQI: 8.3 ■

Well# 7 Sample 7

Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.55	1.66	
	2	33.74	1.05	
	3	35.13	1.04	
	4	36.56	0.98	
	5	37.30	2.73	

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Well# 7 Sample 7				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	6	37.85	3.62	
	7	38.74	5.74	
	8	40.03	6.46	
	9	41.06	10.52	
	10	42.15	13.02	
	11	43.19	9.50	
	12	43.83	36.46	
	13	45.27	8.34	
	14	46.16	15.10	
	15	46.61	14.95	
	16	48.49	14.20	
	17	49.57	7.18	
	18	51.21	38.11	

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Well# 8 Sample 8

8

Well# 8 Sample 8

Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area
1	18S	42.95	45.10	4.61	17.63
2	28S	50.20	52.75	8.44	32.29

RNA Area: 26.15
 RNA Concentration: 77.39 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 1.83
 RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 8 Sample 8

Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.55	1.54	
	2	44.01	4.43	
	3	51.38	8.50	

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Well# 9 Sample 9

9

Well# 9 Sample 9						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	43.00	45.10	3.91	12.16	
2	28S	50.05	52.70	6.77	21.06	

RNA Area: 32.15
 RNA Concentration: 95.12 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 1.73
 RQI: 9.3 ■

Well# 9 Sample 9				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.55	1.46	
	2	43.91	3.63	
	3	51.28	6.85	

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Well# 10 Sample 10

10

Well# 10 Sample 10						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	42.70	44.90	30.75	16.76	
2	28S	49.85	52.35	65.71	35.80	

RNA Area: 183.52
 RNA Concentration: 543.01 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.14
 RQI: 9.9 ■

Well# 10 Sample 10				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.55	1.59	
	2	28.65	2.30	
	3	43.20	0.43	
	4	43.70	28.80	
	5	46.70	0.51	

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Well# 10 Sample 10				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	6	48.25	0.38	
	7	51.00	77.70	

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Well# 11 Sample 11

11

Well# 11 Sample 11						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	42.80	44.80	30.80	14.99	
2	28S	49.95	52.60	86.03	41.87	

RNA Area: 205.47
 RNA Concentration: 607.97 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.79
 RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 11 Sample 11				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.55	1.47	
	2	43.84	31.67	
	3	45.20	1.00	
	4	46.20	2.61	
	5	47.35	0.50	

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Well# 11 Sample 11				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	6	49.61	2.05	
	7	51.16	104.87	
	8	53.76	12.90	

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Well# 12 Sample 12

12

Well# 12 Sample 12						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	42.95	44.95	2.49	15.23	
2	28S	50.05	52.45	5.24	32.04	

RNA Area: 16.36
 RNA Concentration: 48.40 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.10
 RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 12 Sample 12				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.55	1.51	
	2	43.89	2.27	
	3	51.22	4.85	